

STUDY OF METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE TECHNOLOGICAL EFFICIENCY OF THE GRINDING DEPARTMENT IN FLOUR MILLING. ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: Grain is an important raw material in food production. From grain crops, the food products necessary for humans — flour and groats — are produced. Grain is a high-calorie product. It contains organic substances valuable to the human body. The basis of grain consists of proteins and carbohydrates. In particular, grain crops contain 10–15%, and legumes 28–30% of high-quality protein. Furthermore, grain and the products derived from it are an important source of vitamins and minerals.

Keywords: Flour yield, rye-wheat flour, hypothesis, roller mill, roller mill (repetition), flutes, grinding rolls.

Introduction: In the production of flour and groats, grain crops such as wheat, rye, rice (paddy), barley, oats, and corn are mainly used as raw materials. In recent years, the production volumes of flour and groats in our country have been steadily increasing, which is associated with population growth, the relevance of food security issues, and the policy of modernizing the food industry.

New production systems created on the basis of modern technologies and advanced scientific research make it possible to increase the nutritional value of flour and groat products, preserve their biologically active properties, and ensure the production of ready-to-eat products. To date, the production of enriched types of flour with high protein content, fibrous substances (fiber), vitamins, and trace elements has been established. Along with this, the production of groats and semi-finished products that significantly reduce cooking time or require no culinary processing at all is expanding.

Flour is a valuable food product obtained by grinding grains of various crops. The type of flour is determined by the crop from which it is obtained. Flour is produced through milling — a series of processes and operations performed on grain and intermediate products formed during the grinding process.

All milling processes are divided into single-stage and repeated-stage. Single-stage grinding is so called because the grain is turned into flour after a single pass through a grinding machine (millstones or hammer mills). In single-stage grinding, wholemeal flour (without sifting out bran) with a specified yield is produced, as well as gray sifted flour, sifted through dense sieves.

A modern flour mill uses only repeated-stage processes, in which flour is produced by repeatedly passing the material through grinding and sifting machines. The sequential action on the grain ensures gradual grinding, which accelerates the conversion into flour of the

endosperm, which is more fragile than the bran. Thus, the principle of processing grain into flour involves repeated selective grinding of the endosperm and sorting of the grinding products after each stage, with gradual extraction of flour and separation of bran.

The following types of wheat flour are produced: Extra grade, first grade, second grade, and wholemeal flour (obtained by simple grinding without sifting off the grain husks). The grade of flour is determined by the quantitative ratio of the anatomical parts of the grain in its composition. This means that in grade milling, extra-grade flour is produced from the central part of the wheat grain endosperm, first-grade flour from the middle part, and second-grade flour from the peripheral zone.

Flour yield is the amount of flour obtained as a result of milling. Yield is expressed as a percentage of the mass of processed grain. When processing whole grain into flour, it can be 100% (practically 99.5%). However, with such a yield, the flour may have defects (grittiness, altered taste, poorer color). Flour with this yield is not produced. In our country, the following flour yield standards are established: Wheat: 96% — wholemeal (single-grade); 85% — second grade (single-grade); 78% — two-grade and three-grade; 75% — three-grade and single-grade; 72% — first grade (single-grade). Rye: 95% — wholemeal; 87% — debranned; 63% — sifted (all single-grade). Single-grade flour is produced from a mixture of wheat and rye grains: wheat-rye flour with a yield of 96% and rye-wheat flour with a yield of 95%. In addition, to assess wheat varieties for baking, flour with a yield of 70% is produced on experimental laboratory mills.

Grinding processes are widely used in various industries. To obtain a bulk material from solids consisting of particles of a certain size, they are ground in various ways. There are two methods of grinding a solid: simple (ordinary) and selective.

If the product being ground is homogeneous in chemical composition and structural-mechanical properties of all its parts and is ground to a specified particle size, such grinding is called simple.

If the solid being ground is heterogeneous in its chemical composition and structural-mechanical properties, then by targeted intensification of the impact, various properties of the solid's components can be activated. By applying different methods, under the same force impact on the solid, particles differing in size and chemical composition can be obtained. To achieve this goal, grinding in one stage is not enough; it must be repeated multiple times. At each stage, the ground fractions having different sizes and quality are separated by sifting.

This method of grinding is called selective. The selective grinding method is the main one for obtaining several grades of flour from wheat and rye grain prepared for milling.

By grinding a solid, bulk particles of a certain size are obtained from it. This material can be a final product or undergo additional processing to obtain different grades of product. The destruction of a solid to create a mixture is called the simple grinding method. A solid can be heterogeneous in composition; in such a case, during selective grinding of the solid, homogeneous components are separated from it. In the selective grinding method, this process is repeated several times. In the process of obtaining grade flour from wheat and rye grains, the mechanical structure of the endosperm and fruit shells of the grain after hydrothermal treatment (HTT) changes in a positive direction. The main criteria for evaluating the efficiency of the grinding process of a solid, including grain, are as follows:

— degree of grinding; the amount of energy consumption of the process depends on the specific load supplied to the working elements of the grinding machine. The theory of grinding

consists of two hypotheses, of which the "surface" hypothesis was proposed in 1867 by Rittinger, and the "volume" hypothesis in 1874 by V. L. Kirpichev. As a result of grinding, a solid breaks down into many small particles and new surfaces are formed.

Grinding is carried out by crushing, impact, compression, and shear, wherein compressive and shear deformations occur in the body. Under the action of an external force, stresses arise in the body, microcracks appear in it, and due to irreversible destruction, the body turns into new particles. To overcome the strength of the material, energy is expended on breaking intermolecular bonds, forming a new surface, as well as on wear and deformation of the working elements of the grinding equipment.

In the process of preparing grain for simple grinding, the main attention is paid to cleaning the grain batch from impurities. For this purpose, air-sieve separators, aspirators, trieurs, and destoners are used. The grain surface is treated in special machines with metal or even abrasive cylinders (therefore this type of flour is called wholemeal). Sometimes intensive peeling machines of the ZShN type are also used, in which up to 4% of the grain shell can be removed and its ash content reduced by 0.07–0.10%.

Factors affecting the efficiency of a roller mill in the grinding process. It has been established that the efficiency of grinding grain and its milling products is influenced by many factors, the most important of which are: the gap between the rolls, the flute slope, the mutual arrangement of the flutes, the flute density, the peripheral and relative speed of the rolls, as well as the specific load on the rolls.

Size of the inter-roll gap. Changing the gap between the grinding rolls leads to a change in the extraction rate. This is especially noticeable when the inter-roll gap is significantly smaller than the size of the particles being ground.

In grinding systems, the consistency of the inter-roll gap is of particular importance. Therefore, the requirements for the accuracy of the cylindrical shape of the rolls, their bending rigidity, the degree of imbalance of the drive pulley and the inter-roll transmission gears, as well as the quality of the bearings, must be very high. Otherwise, it will be difficult to achieve stability of the inter-roll gap and, consequently, consistency of the extraction rate.

With a change in the working distance between the grinding rolls, the particle size index of the grind changes. Therefore, maintaining a constant working distance between the rolls is of particular importance. To ensure the stability of the working distance between the rolls, the following requirements are imposed:

- The cylindrical shape of the rolls must be manufactured with very high precision;
- The bending rigidity of the rolls must be high;
- The imbalance index of the rolls, as well as the inter-roll transmission pulleys and gears, must be minimal (manufactured with high precision);
- The quality of the bearings in the roller mill must be very high.

Influence of roll flute parameters on the grinding process: The shape of the flutes (teeth) also has a great influence on the grinding process. Therefore, in grade flour milling, fluted rolls are used on the break, scratch, and last reduction systems of roller mills. On the reduction systems, however, rolls with a rough surface are used. The flutes on the roll surface are not located parallel to the roll axis, but at a certain angle, and this indicator is expressed as a percentage (flute slope). As the flute slope angle increases, the grinding intensity increases.

The shape of the flutes (cross-sectional profile) has a significant effect on the grinding process, the quality indicators of the ground product, the capacity of the roll pair, and the

electricity consumption. Based on research and practical experience of flour mills, various flute profiles are used, taking into account the range of flour, the total yield, and the type and quality of the grain raw material being processed.

Fig. 1. Shape and profile of flutes:

a – general view; b – cross-section.

Flute slope. The flutes on the roll are not located parallel to the generatrix (axis), but at a certain angle. The magnitude of this angle (slope) is measured as a percentage. An increase in the flute slope, all other conditions being equal, leads to an increase in grinding intensity, as the distance between the intersection points of the flute crests of the paired rolls decreases. Since the flute slope angle is smaller than the friction angle of the products being ground, no sliding (shear) of the product along the flute occurs.

Mutual arrangement of flutes. The mutual arrangement of the flutes of the paired rolls has a great influence on grinding, which is associated with a change in the cutting angle $\phi\phi$. The design of the roller mill and the rolls, the asymmetry of the flute profile (different angles $\alpha\alpha$ and $\beta\beta$), as well as the difference in peripheral speeds of the paired rolls, determine four possible options for the mutual arrangement of the flutes relative to each other.

Fig. 2. Options for the mutual arrangement of flutes on paired rolls:

a – “crest to crest” b – “groove to groove”.

With the "crest to crest" flute arrangement, both crests of the paired rolls cut into the particle as it enters the grinding zone. Since the fast-running roll leads the slow-running one, its flutes shear off part of the grain, while the crest faces of the slow-running roll hold the particle. With the "crest to crest" arrangement, the bran is destroyed much more intensively along with the endosperm. This is impractical in multi-grade milling of wheat and rye, especially when the moisture content of the grain being processed is insufficient. In this case, more coarse fractions are produced and fewer medium and fine grits. Under the same grinding conditions, the average ash content of the extracted grits and dunts is higher than with the "groove to groove" flute arrangement.

The "crest to crest" arrangement is recommended when processing wheat with a vitreousness of less than 40% for bread flour, as well as when grinding durum wheat for pasta products.

When grinding wheat with a vitreousness of more than 40% for bread-baking purposes, the "groove to groove" arrangement is recommended. With this arrangement, the particle being ground is first flattened, and then, due to the lead of one roll over the other, the groove of the flute of the fast-running roll shears the layers of the particle held by the groove of the flute of the slow-running roll. This results in a gentler action on the particle, since in this case the sharp edges practically do not participate in the deformation of the product.

The "crest to groove" or "groove to crest" arrangements are used in exceptional cases. In this case, the grinding results occupy an intermediate position compared to the "crest to crest" or "groove to groove" arrangements. The flutes of the fast-running roll wear out 1.5–2 times faster than those of the paired slow-running roll.

Flute density. The flute density (the number of flutes per 1 cm of the roll circumference) in the same systems depends on the type and size of the particles being ground. The smaller the size of the particles being ground, the higher the flute density should be. However, with an increase in flute density, the flute height and its cross-sectional area decrease, which leads to a reduction in its service life.

Research has shown that with any mutual arrangement of the flutes, an increase in flute density increases the yield of coarse grits and the total extraction volume. This can be explained

by the fact that the flutes of the fast-running roll exert a repeated action on the product during its passage through the grinding zone.

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